

Health-Aware Non-Intrusive Load Monitoring Using Dual-Branch Attention Network and Variance-Anchored XGBoost Classifier

Ankit Ambasta

School of Computer Science and Engineering
Vellore Institute of Technology
Vellore, India
ambastaankit8@gmail.com

Abstract—Smart meters are now prevalent in most households, enabling aggregate energy monitoring. However, existing Non-Intrusive Load Monitoring (NILM) systems focus primarily on energy disaggregation and largely overlook appliance health assessment. This paper proposes a health-aware NILM framework combining a Dual-Branch Attention Network for Energy Disaggregation (DBAN-ED) with a Variance-anchored XGBoost classifier for Anomaly Detection (VXGB-AD). The DBAN-ED module employs two parallel 1D-CNN branches with kernel sizes 3 and 4, followed by a multi-head attention layer, to disaggregate individual appliance power traces from 8-second aggregate signals. The VXGB-AD module extracts 12 reference-anchored statistical features per activation cycle and classifies each cycle into four health severity levels: Normal, Low, Medium, and High. The complete system is evaluated on the public CLEAN REFIT House 2 dataset across five common household appliances. Results demonstrate that the proposed model outperforms CNN, LSTM, GRU, DTW, and Random Forest baselines in accuracy, F1-score, Mean Absolute Error (MAE), and Signal Aggregate Error (SAE), achieving 0.977 accuracy and F1-score on microwave anomaly detection and 0.958 accuracy on microwave energy disaggregation.

Index Terms—Non-Intrusive Load Monitoring, Energy Disaggregation, Anomaly Detection, Convolutional Neural Network, Multi-Head Attention, XGBoost, Appliance Health Monitoring

I. INTRODUCTION

Non-Intrusive Load Monitoring (NILM) allows precise estimation of per-appliance energy consumption without deploying additional sensors on individual devices. By analysing the aggregate power signal from a single smart meter, NILM estimates the contribution of each appliance, making it a cost-effective and scalable approach to energy management.

Since Hart’s foundational work in 1992, NILM has evolved from steady-state signal analysis to deep learning-based approaches employing CNNs, LSTMs, and GRUs. However, the predominant focus of recent literature remains on improving disaggregation accuracy, with appliance health assessment receiving considerably less attention. This is a critical gap: household appliances degrade over time through motor wear, clogged filters, and heating element deterioration. Without a mechanism to detect such degradation, malfunctions go unnoticed until a total breakdown occurs, resulting in unexpected repair costs and energy waste.

Existing anomaly detection techniques, such as Dynamic Time Warping (DTW) and Random Forest classifiers, are typically deployed separately from the load disaggregation pipeline, requiring large databases of reference signatures and substantial computational resources. Furthermore, most NILM models are designed for high-frequency laboratory data and do not generalise well to the 8-second sampling intervals common in commercial smart meters.

This paper addresses these limitations by proposing an integrated, health-aware NILM framework that performs both energy disaggregation and appliance health grading in a single end-to-end pipeline. The key contributions are:

- A dual-branch 1D-CNN with multi-head attention (DBAN-ED) for accurate energy disaggregation from low-frequency (8 s) aggregate signals.
- A variance-anchored XGBoost classifier (VXGB-AD) that assigns four-level health severity labels (Normal, Low, Medium, High) to each appliance activation cycle.
- A comprehensive evaluation on the CLEAN REFIT House 2 dataset covering five appliances, with comparisons against CNN, LSTM, GRU, DTW, and Random Forest baselines.
- A lightweight, reproducible open-source implementation in PyTorch and XGBoost that operates on standard consumer hardware without GPU requirement at inference time.

II. RELATED WORK

Lee and Moon [1] employed LSTM and GRU networks for NILM, incorporating user location as an auxiliary feature. Their GRU model outperformed factorial hidden Markov models in accuracy and F1-score but did not address anomalous or faulty energy consumption patterns.

Dash and Sahoo [2] proposed a health-monitoring NILM system using DTW distance relative to a reference profile. While the approach yields interpretable results for low, moderate, and high fault levels, DTW is sensitive to noise and scale changes and demands large template storage.

Zhou et al. [11] combined CNN and LSTM in a hybrid architecture for NILM, demonstrating improved performance over individual models. However, the architecture targets

disaggregation only and requires substantial labelled data. The success of this CNN-LSTM combination motivated the multi-scale convolutional branches in the proposed model.

Sudoso and Piccialli [9] used an attention-based encoder-decoder for NILM, showing that focusing on critical time steps improves disaggregation over plain sequence-to-sequence models. Their work directly informed the multi-head attention module in DBAN-ED.

Irani Azad et al. [4] proposed a transformer-based architecture with temporal pooling, achieving superior F1-scores over CNN and RNN models. Despite strong disaggregation performance, health status analysis was not considered.

Lin et al. [13] added self-attention after multi-scale convolutions for simultaneous regression and classification, supporting the feature concatenation design used here.

Sykiotis et al. [10] applied transformer-based attention for energy disaggregation, showing robustness to noisy low-frequency smart meter data, though anomaly detection was absent.

Research Gap: None of the above works integrates a dual-stream deep learning architecture for energy disaggregation with a variance-sensitive machine learning model for anomaly detection within a single pipeline operating at 8-second sampling intervals.

III. SYSTEM DESIGN

A. Overall Architecture

The proposed system follows a two-stage sequential pipeline as illustrated in Fig. 1. In Stage 1, the DBAN-ED module accepts the raw aggregate power signal and outputs the estimated appliance-level power trace. In Stage 2, the VXGB-AD module analyses each activation cycle extracted from this trace and assigns a health severity label.

Fig. 1. Overall two-stage pipeline: Energy Disaggregation (DBAN-ED) followed by Anomaly Detection (VXGB-AD).

The pipeline is entirely offline and modular, allowing independent development and evaluation of each stage while maintaining a seamless end-to-end workflow.

B. Data Preprocessing

The CLEAN REFIT House 2 CSV file is loaded retaining the aggregate and target appliance columns. Unrealistic spikes (aggregate >20 kW, appliance >4 kW) are removed and replaced with NaNs. Short gaps up to 120 seconds are filled using forward fill; longer gaps are zeroed. Both signals are z-score normalised:

$$x_{\text{norm}} = \frac{x - \mu}{\sigma + 10^{-8}} \quad (1)$$

where μ and σ are the mean and standard deviation of the full series, and the small constant prevents division by zero. Fixed sliding windows are created with input length $L = 2W + 2C + 1 = 75$ samples and output length $2W + 1 = 31$ samples ($W = 15$, $C = 22$). The dataset is split 70%/15%/15% for training, validation, and testing chronologically.

ON/OFF balance is maintained by retaining all ON-state samples and sub-sampling OFF-state samples at a roughly 1:3 ON-to-OFF ratio. Appliance-specific ON thresholds are listed in Table I.

TABLE I
APPLIANCE-SPECIFIC ON THRESHOLDS

Appliance	ON Threshold (W)
Dishwasher	100
Microwave	200
Kettle	800
Washing Machine	200
Fridge	50

IV. METHODOLOGY

A. Energy Disaggregation Module (DBAN-ED)

The DBAN-ED module, shown in Fig. 2, is a sequence-to-subsequence regression network. Two parallel 1D-CNN branches process the 75-sample input window:

$$f_i = \text{ReLU}(\text{Conv1D}(\text{ReLU}(\text{Conv1D}(X, \theta_{i1})), \theta_{i2})) \quad (2)$$

Branch 1 uses kernel size 3 (31 filters) to capture fast transients; Branch 2 uses kernel size 4 (32 filters) to capture slower temporal patterns. The branch outputs are concatenated with the original input to form a $d_{\text{model}} = 64$ dimensional feature vector, which is fed into a 4-head multi-head attention sub-module:

$$\text{att} = \text{LayerNorm}(\text{MHA}(W_q f, W_k f, W_v f) + f) \quad (3)$$

A fully connected layer then produces the 31-point predicted output sequence. Training minimises MAE loss:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{ED}} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N |y_i - \hat{y}_i| \quad (4)$$

using the Adam optimiser (lr = 0.0001), batch size 128, and early stopping with patience 10.

B. Anomaly Detection Module (VXGB-AD)

After disaggregation, activation cycles are extracted using appliance-specific ON thresholds. A healthy activation library is built from training data by computing global statistics: $\text{GLOBAL}_{\text{DUR}}$, $\text{GLOBAL}_{\text{PWR}}$, and $\text{GLOBAL}_{\text{MAX}}$. For each cycle, 12 reference-anchored features are computed:

Fig. 2. DBAN-ED architecture: dual-branch CNN, multi-head attention, and regression output.

$$\text{Duration Ratio} = \frac{L}{\text{GLOBAL}_{\text{DUR}}} \quad (5)$$

$$\text{Mean Ratio} = \frac{\mu}{\text{GLOBAL}_{\text{PWR}}} \quad (6)$$

$$\text{Max Ratio} = \frac{P_{\text{max}}}{\text{GLOBAL}_{\text{MAX}}} \quad (7)$$

along with absolute deviations $|L - \text{GLOBAL}_{\text{DUR}}|$ and $|\mu - \text{GLOBAL}_{\text{PWR}}|$, plus standard statistical measures (std, sum, 25th/75th percentiles).

Artificial anomalies are injected during training by either scaling the magnitude (8% to +35%) or extending the duration (30%–100%), labelled as Low, Medium, or High based on perturbation magnitude.

Features are standardised using StandardScaler and fed into an XGBoost classifier (300 trees, max depth 6, learning rate 0.05, balanced class weights, multi-class softmax objective). The AD module architecture is shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. VXGB-AD architecture: reference-anchored feature extraction and XGBoost classifier.

C. Model Hyperparameters

All hyperparameters used in both stages are listed in Table II. Values were determined through systematic experimentation and early stopping to prevent overfitting.

TABLE II
HYPERPARAMETERS OF THE PROPOSED SYSTEM

Parameter	Value
<i>DBAN-ED (Energy Disaggregation)</i>	
Input window length (samples)	75
Output window length (samples)	31
Batch size	128
Learning rate (Adam)	0.0001
Maximum epochs	100
Early stopping patience	10
Branch 1 filters / kernel size	31 / 3
Branch 2 filters / kernel size	32 / 4
Attention heads	4
Feature dimension d_{model}	64
Sampling interval	8 s
<i>VXGB-AD (Anomaly Detection)</i>	
Number of estimators (trees)	300
Maximum tree depth	6
XGBoost learning rate	0.05
Objective	multi:softmax
Class weights	Balanced
Reference features per cycle	12

D. Evaluation Metrics

Energy Disaggregation is evaluated using MAE and Signal Aggregate Error (SAE):

$$\text{MAE} = \frac{1}{DE} \sum_{e=1}^E \sum_{d=1}^D |y(d) - \hat{y}(d)| \quad (8)$$

$$\text{SAE} = \frac{1}{E} \sum_{e=1}^E \frac{1}{D} \left| \sum_{d=1}^D y(d) - \sum_{d=1}^D \hat{y}(d) \right| \quad (9)$$

ON/OFF classification accuracy and macro F1-score are also reported. Anomaly Detection is evaluated using binary accuracy and macro F1-score (Normal vs. Anomalous).

V. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

A. Energy Disaggregation Results

Table III reports MAE and SAE for all five appliances. The proposed DBAN-ED consistently outperforms CNN, LSTM, and GRU baselines. The largest improvements are observed for the Microwave (MAE reduced from 0.193 to 0.101, a 48% improvement) and Kettle (SAE of 0.059, the lowest across all models). The Dishwasher MAE improves from 0.497 (CNN) to 0.327.

TABLE III
ED ERROR METRICS — MAE AND SAE

Appliance	CNN		LSTM		GRU		Proposed	
	MAE	SAE	MAE	SAE	MAE	SAE	MAE	SAE
Dishwasher	0.497	0.281	0.416	0.228	0.435	0.245	0.327	0.186
Microwave	0.193	0.153	0.131	0.111	0.441	0.256	0.101	0.088
Kettle	0.281	0.154	0.189	0.092	0.179	0.081	0.098	0.059
Washing Machine	0.268	0.228	0.188	0.163	0.197	0.171	0.174	0.145
Fridge	0.380	0.356	—	—	—	—	0.587	0.560

Table IV reports ON/OFF classification accuracy and F1-score. The Microwave achieves 0.958 accuracy and 0.923

F1-score; the Kettle reaches 0.951 accuracy. The Fridge remains challenging owing to its low-amplitude, high-frequency oscillations, though the F1-score of 0.724 marks a notable improvement over the CNN baseline.

TABLE IV
ED CLASSIFICATION METRICS — ACCURACY AND F1-SCORE

Appliance	CNN		LSTM		GRU		Proposed	
	Acc	F1	Acc	F1	Acc	F1	Acc	F1
Dishwasher	0.777	0.705	0.822	0.746	0.810	0.736	0.888	0.823
Microwave	0.892	0.824	0.951	0.911	0.810	0.737	0.958	0.923
Kettle	0.823	0.713	0.865	0.764	0.884	0.791	0.951	0.899
Washing Machine	0.816	0.700	0.867	0.731	0.870	0.745	0.881	0.768
Fridge	0.752	0.544	—	—	—	—	0.737	0.724

Sample ED+AD dashboard plots for representative appliances are shown in Figs. 4–5.

Fig. 4. ED+AD results dashboard — Microwave (REFIT House 2).

Fig. 5. ED+AD results dashboard — Kettle (REFIT House 2).

B. Anomaly Detection Results

Table V presents AD accuracy and macro F1-score. VXGB-AD outperforms both DTW and Random Forest baselines across all appliances. The Microwave achieves 0.977 accuracy and F1-score. The Dishwasher records 0.810/0.809 and the Kettle 0.851/0.837. The Fridge, tested without a DTW baseline, achieves 0.910 accuracy and 0.914 F1-score.

TABLE V
ANOMALY DETECTION RESULTS — ACCURACY AND F1-SCORE

Appliance	DTW		RF		Proposed	
	Acc	F1	Acc	F1	Acc	F1
Dishwasher	0.558	0.217	0.781	0.757	0.810	0.809
Microwave	—	—	0.963	0.963	0.977	0.977
Kettle	0.505	0.659	0.781	0.757	0.851	0.837
Washing Machine	0.608	0.419	0.757	0.728	0.750	0.756
Fridge	—	—	—	—	0.910	0.914

C. t-SNE Feature Space Analysis

Fig. 6 shows the t-SNE projection of the 12-dimensional AD feature space for the Microwave. Normal activations form a dense cluster, while Low, Medium, and High anomaly classes separate distinctly along power-variation and cycle-time axes, confirming the discriminative power of the reference-anchored features.

Fig. 6. t-SNE visualisation of the AD feature space — Microwave.

For the Dishwasher, normal activations cluster to the left while anomalous points disperse vertically. The Fridge and Washing Machine exhibit greater overlap between Normal and Low severity classes, consistent with their lower F1-scores and more variable power profiles.

D. Anomaly Degree Classification

Figs. 7 and 8 compare ground-truth and predicted anomaly severity distributions for the Microwave and Dishwasher respectively. For the Microwave, predictions match closely across all four classes, with only minor deviation in the Medium class. For the Dishwasher, Low severity is slightly underestimated and Medium slightly overestimated, which accounts for the marginal gap between accuracy and F1-score.

VI. DISCUSSION

The dual-branch CNN architecture provides complementary feature extraction: the size-3 kernel captures sharp power transients (e.g., microwave on-switching), while the size-4

Fig. 7. Anomaly Degree Classification — Microwave.

Fig. 8. Anomaly Degree Classification — Dishwasher.

kernel models slower-evolving patterns (e.g., dishwasher wash cycles). Multi-head attention dynamically weights the most informative time steps, which is especially beneficial at the low 8-second sampling frequency where appliance signatures are compressed.

The variance-anchored feature design in VXGB-AD is the key enabler for robust anomaly detection. By expressing each cycle’s statistics relative to global healthy baselines rather than as absolute values, the classifier becomes resistant to household-specific usage patterns while still detecting deviations indicative of degradation.

The Fridge remains the most challenging appliance for energy disaggregation due to its rapid, low-amplitude compressor cycling. The normalised MAE of 0.587 is higher than for other appliances; however, the improved F1-score of 0.724 versus 0.544 (CNN baseline) demonstrates progress. For anomaly detection, the Fridge achieves the second-best result (0.910 accuracy), likely because compressor anomalies manifest as distinct duty-cycle changes that are well captured by duration-ratio features.

The Washing Machine poses challenges for both stages owing to its complex multi-stage power profile (pre-wash, wash, rinse, spin). The F1-score of 0.768 for ED and 0.756

for AD are the lowest among the five appliances, suggesting that phase-dependent or multi-resolution features could further improve performance.

All experiments were conducted on Google Colab with a T4 GPU for training (under 2 hours for ED) and are reproducible using fixed random seeds. Inference requires no GPU, making deployment on consumer hardware practical.

VII. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This paper presented a health-aware NILM framework combining DBAN-ED and VXGB-AD in a single two-stage pipeline. The proposed system accurately disaggregates per-appliance power consumption and simultaneously grades appliance health into four severity levels using only 8-second aggregate smart meter data.

Across five household appliances, the proposed model outperforms CNN, LSTM, GRU, DTW, and Random Forest baselines in both energy disaggregation and anomaly detection. Notably, the Microwave achieves 0.958 accuracy in ED and 0.977 in AD, while the Kettle records the lowest SAE of 0.059.

Future work will extend evaluation to additional houses in the REFIT dataset and to entirely new households to assess cross-building generalisation. Real-time deployment on edge devices through model quantisation and continual online learning is a natural next step. For complex multi-stage appliances such as the Washing Machine, incorporating transformer-based temporal modelling or phase-aware features may further reduce residual disaggregation errors and improve low-severity anomaly detection.

REFERENCES

- [1] M.-H. Lee and H.-J. Moon, “Nonintrusive load monitoring using recurrent neural networks with occupants’ location information in residential buildings,” *Energies*, vol. 16, no. 9, 2023.
- [2] S. Dash and N. C. Sahoo, “Non-intrusive appliance energy and health monitoring using attention-assisted deep learning model and dynamic time warping distance-based algorithm,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 13, 2025.
- [3] A. Gao, J. Zheng, F. Mei, H. Sha, Y. Xie, K. Li, and Y. Liu, “Non-intrusive multi-label load monitoring via transfer and contrastive learning architecture,” *Int. J. Electr. Power Energy Syst.*, vol. 154, 2023.
- [4] M. Irani Azad, R. Rajabi, and A. Estebarsari, “Non-intrusive load monitoring using deep neural networks: A review,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:2306.05017*, 2023.
- [5] H. Kim, M. Marwah, M. Arlitt, G. Lyon, and J. Han, “Unsupervised disaggregation of low frequency power measurements,” in *Proc. SIAM Int. Conf. Data Mining*, 2011.
- [6] D. Murray, L. Stankovic, and V. Stankovic, “REFIT: Electrical load measurements (cleaned),” 2016.
- [7] A. G. Putrada *et al.*, “GRU with multi-feature input for appliance classification in NILM,” in *Proc. IEEE Int. Conf. Smart Computing (SMARTCOMP)*, 2022.
- [8] H. Rafiq, H. Zhang, H. Li, and M. K. Ochani, “Regularized LSTM based deep learning model: First step towards real-time non-intrusive load monitoring,” in *Proc. IEEE Int. Conf. Sustainable Energy, Grids and Networks (SEGE)*, 2018.
- [9] A. M. Sudoso and V. Piccialli, “Improving non-intrusive load disaggregation through an attention-based deep neural network,” *Energies*, vol. 14, no. 4, 2021.
- [10] S. Sykiotis, M. Kaselimi, A. Doulamis, and N. Doulamis, “ELECTRICity: An efficient transformer for non-intrusive load monitoring,” *Sensors*, vol. 22, no. 8, 2022.
- [11] X. Zhou, S. Li, C. Liu, H. Zhu, N. Dong, and T. Xiao, “Non-intrusive load monitoring using a CNN-LSTM-RF model considering label correlation and class-imbalance,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, 2021.

- [12] A. Zoha, A. Gluhak, M. A. Imran, and S. Rajasegarar, "Non-intrusive load monitoring approaches for disaggregated energy sensing: A survey," *Sensors*, vol. 12, no. 12, 2012.
- [13] J. Lin, J. Ma, J. Zhu, and H. Liang, "Deep domain adaptation for non-intrusive load monitoring based on a knowledge transfer learning network," *IEEE Trans. Smart Grid*, vol. 13, no. 1, 2022.